

FNS – Cloud

Food Nutrition Security

Food Nutrition Security Cloud

Deliverable 4.6

Report on data quality and usability assessment strategies to support assessment and compatibility of intake and consumer behaviour datasets for FNS-Cloud

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1 Publishable summary

In the era of increasing data reuse, it is imperative for the maintenance of scientific quality that all data selected for secondary analysis be *fit for the intended purpose*. Whilst it is true that many datasets *can* be reused the question remains over whether they *should* be. Within FNS-Cloud there is a need for a framework to support the researcher in making that decision. This deliverable primarily captures data from the food intake and lifestyle domain of the FNS-Cloud data map (presented in deliverable 2.1). Therefore, the aim of this deliverable is to describe the development of a quality assessment framework for FNS-Cloud. To achieve this aim markers of quality were identified for dietary intake, lifestyle, demographic, anthropometric and consumer behaviour data where quality was considered at a data collection, data management and data analysis level. These markers then informed the development of flow charts for each data domain. The flow charts comprise a series of questions relating to an aspect of quality specific to each data domain. Individualised messages specific to the answers given to each question were developed to provide the researcher with considerations to support them in their decision of whether the data they have selected is appropriate for their research question. As part of the next phase of implementing the quality assessment into FNS-Cloud, the flow charts will undergo a 2-step evaluation process: 1) internal by partners of FNS-Cloud with domain specific knowledge, 2) external by specific members of the EEAB. It is hoped that the framework will be deployed within FNS Cloud and used by all data users as one of the first steps in identifying datasets suitable for use in their specific analyses.

2 Introduction

There is a need to improve the infrastructure which supports the reuse of data in the food nutrition and security domain ⁽¹⁾. The Food Nutrition and Security Cloud (FNS-Cloud) consortium was developed with the overarching aim to overcome fragmentation issues within FNS data by integrating existing data and developing an infrastructure and services to exploit food, nutrition and security data (data, knowledge, tools – resources) for a range of purposes ⁽²⁾. Specialised data repositories have been created in recent years bringing together data for specific research areas, for example repositories in the Life Sciences ^(3; 4; 5), however, these are highly specialised and only accept datasets which fit into their data models ⁽¹⁾. In response to this, several multipurpose repositories have emerged, such as Fairspace (<https://www.thehyve.nl/services/fairspace>), Zenodo (<http://zenodo.org/>) and Mendeley (<https://data.mendeley.com/>) ⁽⁶⁾. Generally, whilst these repositories have few restrictions and accept many different data types in varying formats, they do not provide integration or harmonisation services for the deposited data, and have few requirements for data descriptors ⁽¹⁾; thus, exacerbate as opposed to ameliorate fragmentation problems in FNS resources. An FNS specific repository and a specific area for data management and predictive modelling is still lacking. A key aim of the FNS-Cloud project is to overcome limitations of current repositories for better understanding and exploitation of existing data, benefiting European citizens and adding-value to previous publicly funded research. The main objective is to prepare the FNS Cloud by defining and implementing the technical components to enable integration of the Services.

The principles of FAIR underpin data reuse and act as guidelines for data holders/researchers to put data in a position to be reused ⁽¹⁾. FAIR stands for findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable; definitions of each of these terms are displayed in Table 2.1. It is known that good data management is essential to its reuse after publication ⁽¹⁾. However, in the absence of appropriate IT infrastructure to house data its long-term uses are limited and data (which is often publicly funded) cannot be fully exploited, thus hindering scientific progress and the maximum use of funding resources. In order to combat this, the 4 FAIR principles were established as a guide for researchers to ensure that maximal benefits can be derived from their data, tools, services and algorithms ⁽¹⁾. Applying the FAIR principles to research data will be mutually beneficial to both scientific research and society. Recognising this, the European Commission (EC) has established an expert group which aims to turn the concept of FAIR data into reality in order to open up science and research ⁽⁷⁾, and through EOSC, to federate existing research data infrastructures in Europe and realise a web of FAIR data and related services for science, making research data interoperable and machine actionable ⁽⁸⁾.

Table 2.1: FAIR principles ⁽¹⁾

Principle	Definition
Findable	Ability to find data through assignment of a globally unique and persistent identifier; describing data with rich metadata; including the identifier of the data alongside the metadata; and, indexing of data and metadata in a searchable resource
Accessible	Metadata and data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol; the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable; the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary; metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available
Interoperable	Metadata and data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation; metadata and data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles; metadata and data include qualified references to other metadata and data
Reusable	Metadata and data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes and are released with a clear and accessible data usage license; metadata and data are associated with detailed provenance; metadata and data meet domain-relevant community standards

At present, there are limited large scale pan-European dietary intake datasets ^(9; 10; 11), but many smaller and more focused (national, cohort specific datasets) exist. Using FAIR principles to ensure the inter-operability and merging of available datasets to answer overarching research questions, will enable greater assessment of health and health related outcomes from existing food, nutrition and health datasets.

In addition to applying FAIR principles to combine datasets from different sources, it is important that appropriate data sources are selected for the research question(s) being considered, and that researchers understand and consider the quality and provenance of the data being used ^(12; 13). To ensure high quality research it is imperative that the datasets being combined are of sufficient quality to be merged and that the datasets are fit for the intended research purpose ⁽¹⁴⁾. The development of resources to assess whether datasets from different sources are of sufficient quality for the intended use will support the reuse of existing datasets within the FNS area.

When referring to the quality of specific datasets it is important to note that this must be considered on an individual research question basis. Each researcher/data user must make their own assessment of whether the datasets that they have selected are appropriate for their specific research question. The FNS-Cloud quality resources which will be developed are intended to be used as a guide for researchers/data users to assess whether certain datasets are suitable for their specific research question, but the final decision will be made by the researcher/data user.

A data map for the FNS-Cloud project was developed in Deliverable 2.1 which outlines the data areas included in the project under 3 domains: agri-Food, nutrition and health, food intake and lifestyle. Within this deliverable, data from the food intake and lifestyle (dietary intake, lifestyle, demographic, consumer behaviour), and nutrition and health (anthropometric) domains will be considered. The overall aim of this deliverable is to describe the development of a quality assessment framework for FNS-Cloud enabling researchers to assess whether the data are of appropriate quality or 'fit for the intended purpose'. Before this framework can be developed, there is a need to understand the factors influencing the quality of data to be considered; therefore, this overall aim will be achieved through three main objectives:

- 1) Summary of progress to date by previous endeavours considering quality of data
- 2) Description of markers of quality for dietary intake, lifestyle, demographic, anthropometric and consumer behaviour data at each level, namely, collection, coding and management, uses and analysis
- 3) Development of a quality assessment framework for FNS-Cloud consisting of strategies and standard operating procedures to support the exploitation of intake and consumer behaviour datasets.

2.1 Current state of the art

There have been numerous previous endeavours which have focused on improving and understanding factors influencing quality across different aspects of FNS data. These have focused on different aspects of data including defining the quality of datasets ⁽¹⁵⁾, selecting tools for data collection ⁽¹⁶⁾, and the creation of tools, services and a research infrastructure to support the sharing of data from nutritional studies ⁽¹⁷⁾. The progress made in this area by some of the more recent and relevant projects which have developed tools or quality assessment frameworks have been summarised below.

In 2014, a suggested framework for the quality of big data was developed by representatives of national statistics offices and was published as a deliverable by the UNECE/HLG project ⁽¹⁵⁾. This framework consisted of 3 phases for assessing quality of big data: input (the collection phase of the data); throughput (the processing and analysing phases of data); output (the evaluation and dissemination phases). This framework has a hierarchical structure consisting of 3 hyper dimensions with quality dimensions nested within each, namely, source, metadata and data. The source refers to the type of data. Metadata refers to the description of the data, its contents and the processes applied

to it. The data hyper dimension refers to the quality of the data itself. This framework also proposed 3 principles for the evaluation of big data, primarily:

- *Fitness for use*- the data selected should be suitable for use for the intended research purpose.
- *Generic and flexible*- the quality indicators within the quality framework are developed to reflect the quality assessment under each context.
- *Efforts vs. gain*- the overall assessment of fitness for use of the data can only be performed once all quality dimensions and relevant indicators have been assessed. To balance the effort involved in assessing data quality and the added values of using the data a set of minimum requirements to be met should be identified.

Focusing on the data collection side, within the DIETary Assessment Tool NETwork (DIET@NET) project Best Practice Guidelines (BPGs) for researchers on selecting the most appropriate dietary assessment tool were established through expert consensus ⁽¹⁶⁾. This expert group found that to choose the optimal dietary assessment tool, researchers should consider the cost, measurement error (e.g., underreporting) and validation associated with different tools. Failure to acknowledge error can lead to misleading results. The developed guidelines can be broken into 4 stages and if followed should result in stronger research and quality of research findings.

- Stage I focuses on defining what is to be measured in terms of dietary intake (what? who? and when?)
- Stage II looks at different types of dietary assessment tools
- Stage III evaluates published validation studies to select the most appropriate dietary assessment tool
- Stage IV involves going through the implementation of the chosen tool to consider sources of potential biases ⁽¹⁶⁾. These guidelines are accessible through the Nutritools website (www.nutritools.org)

QuaLiFY (Grant agreement No. 613783, EIT Food grant No. 18064) aimed to deliver a digital platform (Quisper®) to support delivery of personalised nutrition services in Europe by health and wellbeing SMEs, based on a non-profit organisation. Quisper® aims to deliver high quality, scientifically validated diet and nutritional data and knowledge, supporting personalised diet, nutrition and health information, for improved public health. Through independent experts, external scientific advisory board quality assessment checklists were developed for various service portfolios in the area of personalised nutrition, namely, genetic testing, food supplements, food composition databases, dietary reference values, nutrition apps, and nutrition advice algorithms. Each area consisted of quality dimensions sub-divided into quality criteria each of which have indicators/questions, to

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support the assessment of quality for each domain. The indicators/questions can be answered as Yes/No/not applicable (N/A) and translate to scores of 1/0/0, within an overall quality framework. Overall scores are calculated using the mean (sum of 'Yes's / (number of questions – the N/A answers)) and then the mean score converted into an overall quality rating using a 5-star system. One star '*' symbolizes poor, two stars '**' fair, three stars '***' average, four stars '****' good and five stars '*****' excellent service quality. In addition to the checklists, lists of 'quality standards' were developed for each area.

Within ENPADASI ⁽¹⁷⁾, an open access research infrastructure for all nutritional mechanistic, interventional and epidemiological studies a tool for collecting study metadata was also developed, using work completed within the DEDIPAC project as a template ^(17; 18) and a checklist developed on minimal study information requirements to be added as metadata to studies to boost integration capacity. To combine studies, the Phenotype database and Opal/DataShield were integrated under The Data Sharing Initiative for Nutrition (DASH-IN) infrastructure, which contains options for assessing data, and performing integrated analysis on multiple studies to facilitate further exploitation of data ⁽¹⁷⁾.

There has been a number of other endeavours which have aimed to improve quality within the area of FNS. The TDS-Exposure project developed a quality management framework to improve quality and harmonization of Total Diet Study practices in Europe ⁽¹⁹⁾. The European Food Information Resource Network (EuroFIR) supports use of existing food composition data and future resources through cooperation and harmonization of data quality, functionality and global standards. EuroFIR provides a comprehensive European online resource for food composition data compilers and users ^(20; 21). Furthermore, EuroFIR developed the eBASIS and ePlantLibra databases to give compilers and users access to information on bioactive components in plant foods and plant food supplements ^(22; 23). The databases also incorporate a quality scheme, assessing sampling and analytical methods.

Whilst considerable progress has been made in recent years to improve quality within FNS research (Table 2.2) gaps remain in terms of assessing the quality of specific domains of data and collected datasets. We know that FNS data is rarely collected in isolation and demographic, health and lifestyle data are frequently collected as complementary data. This data is analysed alongside FNS data to provide further context to the FNS data with regard to differences according to sex, socioeconomic status, age and other demographic parameters, or is used to assess associations between the FNS data and indicators of health or lifestyle indices. It is therefore important to consider quality across a number of domains – dietary intake, consumer behaviour and demographic and lifestyle data - in a systematic manner to allow evaluation for more complex research questions.

Tool/resource name	Project/endeavour	Purpose
Quisper quality standards and checklists	Qualify	quality assessment checklists were developed for various service portfolios in the area of personalised nutrition, namely, genetic testing, food supplements, food composition databases, dietary reference values, nutrition apps, and nutrition advice algorithms
www.nutritools.org	DIET@NET ⁽¹⁶⁾	Best Practice Guidelines for dietary assessment in health research
QMF for Total Diet Studies	TDS-Exposure project ⁽¹⁹⁾	Quality management framework to improve quality and harmonization of Total Diet Study practices in Europe
European online quality resource for food composition data	EuroFIR ⁽²¹⁾	Standardized protocols and quality schemes to compile and manage food composition databases
eBasis	EuroFIR ⁽²²⁾	Internet deployed food composition and biological effects database for plant-based bioactive compounds with putative health benefits
ePlantLibra	EuroFIR ⁽²⁴⁾	Comprehensive database containing quality evaluated information on plant and plant food supplements (PFS), specifically bioactive compound composition, botanical information, beneficial bioactivity data and case-reports of adverse effects as well as composition of potential contaminants
Minimal requirements for study data in nutritional epidemiology	ENPADASI ⁽¹⁷⁾	a checklist on minimal study information requirements to be added as metadata to studies to boost integration capacity

3 Dietary Intake data

3.1 Introduction to dietary intake data

Dietary intake data are used to determine food, nutrient and ingredient intakes at both individual and population levels ⁽²⁵⁾. Dietary data can be assessed in clinical settings to support personalised care, or within population groups for research purposes and to develop government policy and public awareness campaigns ⁽²⁶⁾. In recent years, there has been a drive towards personalised nutrition approaches which use aspects of an individual's demographic characteristics, anthropometric status, genetics or personal preferences to tailor nutrition advice such that they achieve a lasting dietary behaviour change that is beneficial for their health ⁽²⁷⁾. Analysis of dietary intake data can provide information on dietary and meal patterns, food contaminants and residues as well as the association of dietary intake with health outcomes ^{(28) (29)}. Finally, dietary intake information can also be used at the consumer level to support a healthy diet and lifestyle, through informed food choices, to support adherence to specific or population healthy eating recommendations.

3.2 Methods of collection of dietary intake data

Data collection for dietary intake data, has three main facets – each of which need to be properly addressed to maintain quality and accuracy; 1) Identification of food ^(30; 31; 32) 2) quantification of portion size ⁽³³⁾ and 3) conversion to nutrient intake (or increasingly also bioactives), using appropriate analytic measures (e.g. duplicate portion technique) or suitable food composition datasets ^(34; 35).

Dietary intake can be assessed using subjective or objective methods ⁽³⁶⁾. Subjective methods involve self-assessment of diet and include retrospective measures such as 24-hour dietary recalls, food frequency questionnaires (FFQ), diet histories and prospective measures such as dietary records (14). Objective measures include use of nutritional biomarkers ^(37; 38; 39). The subjective self-reported measures of diet are most commonly used in nutritional research, yet they are subject to both random errors and systematic errors (e.g. recall bias, interviewer bias) ⁽⁴⁰⁾. The extent of error differs across different methods. Among the available methods, some are more commonly self-administered (food record, FFQ), while others are supported by trained interviewers (24-hour recall, diet history). The quality of data collected from each method depends on different aspects of data collection and handling and will be considered in this deliverable.

As technology develops there is a need for dietary intake assessment to utilise technological developments to improve the accuracy, scope and reach of intake assessments ⁽⁴¹⁾. EFSA has underlined the need for "initiatives to further develop web-based tools in the area of dietary surveys" ⁽⁴²⁾. Development of novel dietary assessment tools has increased rapidly, with many adopting online, computerised tools for their research to replace traditional methods ^(43; 44). Advantages of online dietary assessment include greater geographical reach, reduced cost, and lower participant burden ⁽⁴⁵⁾. However, many of the challenges associated with traditional assessment, including under and over reporting, remain ⁽⁴⁶⁾. Choosing the most appropriate dietary assessment method depends largely on the specific research or clinical questions and population being considered, timeframe for data collection and resources available for collection and analysis ^(47; 48). Internet- or web-based tools have enabled many of the traditional interviewer-led methods of dietary intake data collection, to transfer to self-administered methods ^(49; 50). Numerous technological advances are being employed in an attempt to reduce some of the limitations of traditional intake collection methods. Barcode scanners and food image processing technology in portable devices allow non-text functionalities to be incorporated while enhancing the accuracy of self-report by increasing user adherence and goal setting features to increase user engagement ⁽⁵¹⁾. Whilst challenges still exist, there are some clear benefits to the researcher in using technology based methods of collection such as cost effectiveness, greater participant reach and time saving through automatic storage of input data and the immediate generation of nutritional outputs ⁽³⁶⁾.

In more recent years, objective measures of dietary intake are being considered in combination with, or to replace traditional methods. These include nutritional biomarkers, which are indicators of dietary exposure assessed through biological sampling. Nutritional biomarkers range from analysis of specific metabolites associated with individual nutrient intake e.g., Urinary N and protein, to complex metabolomic profiling to match specific dietary patterns ⁽⁵²⁾. Whilst such techniques have considerable strengths including removal of recall bias, nutritional biomarkers do not exist for all foods and nutrients and it is challenging to identify compound sources (food sources of nutrient intakes) through biomarker analysis alone ⁽⁵³⁾. Furthermore, most biomarkers only roughly reflect the quantity of food intake and highly depend on the time span between dietary intake and sampling of the biomarkers. However, significant advances in this field have been made in recent years, and it is envisaged that this field will support dietary intake assessment in the near future ⁽³⁷⁾. A brief summary, and outline of strengths and weakness or various intake assessment methods are considered in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Summary of existing novel dietary assessment tools

Methodology	Description	Technology / Tool	Advantages	Disadvantages	Appropriate Use
24-hour Dietary Recall	Retrospective collection of detailed information on all foods and beverages consumed in the preceding 24	Web-based application Examples: Foodbook24 ¹ , ASA24 ² , myfood24 ³	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost/time effectiveness • Greater geographical reach • Standardisation of food probing / questions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Random and systematic error • Limited use among elderly and children • Estimated portion size 	Research Consumer Clinical
Food Frequency Questionnaire	Questionnaire examining frequency of consumption of a certain food or food group over a specified period.	Web-based application Examples: food4me ⁴ , Web-FFQ ⁵	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost/time effectiveness • Greater geographical reach • Collection of complex, accurate data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Random and systematic error • Limited among elderly and children • Crude estimate of habitual intake • Does not account for seasonal / week variation 	Research Consumer
Dietary Record	Dietary records are used to collect detailed food & beverage consumption information over one or more days, at the time of eating occasion.	Web-based questionnaire Examples: NANA ⁶ , Web-PDHQ ⁷ , Food Record ⁸	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Greater geographical reach • Representative of habitual diet • Real-time data available 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Random and systematic error • Limited use among elderly and children • Estimated portion size • Training to use technology 	Research Consumer Clinical
Image Recognition	Use of food / meal images for the automated / semi-automated identification and quantification of foods, to determine nutrient intakes	Electronic Food Photography Examples: mobile telephone food record, TADA ⁹	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction in reporting bias • Lower burden on participant • Captures what foods are eaten in tandem 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accuracy dependent on lighting, food placement and visibility of all foods • Time/cost burden for researcher • Difficulty analysing multiple components 	Commercial Consumer
Food Management		Smart fridge/freezer Examples: SmrtFridge ¹⁰ , HighChest ¹¹	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction in reporting bias • Identifies exact food types/brands • Accurate depiction of household consumption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Privacy concerns • Lack of weight sensors • Not all foods consumed are stored in fridge 	Commercial Consumer
Food Store Loyalty Information		Electronic, point-of-sale consumer data, Tesco Loyalty Programme ¹²	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction in reporting bias • Low time burden on participant • Wealth of consumer data available 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inaccurate analysis of individual diet (representative of household) • Consumers may use multiple stores when buying food items/ no record of food consumed outside the home 	Research Commercial Consumer

1(4), 2(22), 3(23), 4(16), 5(24), 6(18), 7(25), 8(26), 9(19), 10(20), 11(27), 12(21)

3.3 Quality considerations when collecting dietary intake data

Tool Validation

Before using data arising from the use a specific tool or assessment method, researchers should consider how the tool or method was developed and validated to fully understand its use in the given situation and/or population ⁽⁵⁴⁾. Assessment of the validity of dietary intake data arising from any given tool or method is complex, but often relies on 2 principles – comparison to an independent marker or intake (e.g., biomarkers or direct observation), or comparison to a previously validated and established method, with weighed intake often considered as the gold standard method of intake assessment ^(55; 56). Validity, as described here, is therefore dependent on the independent markers and or tools used for comparison, which are often subjectively chosen and will themselves vary, and as such it is important to consider how validity is defined for each tool ^(45; 50; 57; 58).

When considering validity in relation to independent biomarkers, these can include doubly labelled water to measure energy expenditure, 24-hour urinary nitrogen to measure protein intakes, 24-hour urinary potassium and sodium ⁽⁵⁹⁾. Other biomarker classifications include concentration and predictive biomarkers, however these biomarkers are deemed less reliable measures of absolute intake for validation studies ⁽⁶⁰⁾. Whilst less costly and less invasive, comparison of food and nutrient intakes derived from a novel tool or method to an established subjective method is the most common method of ‘validation’, with comparisons usually against 24-hour recalls and/or dietary records ^(49; 55; 58). Collecting intakes from both methods allows statistical analysis to identify reporting differences, inclusion or exclusion of foods or meals, differences in reported and/or assumed portion sizes, and the subsequent impact on nutrient intakes ^(49; 58; 61). Specific statistical comparisons including correlation coefficients which can be used to measure the strength of intakes between the test and reference method, and Bland-Altman analysis to compare the mean differences of the quantitative measures and determine the level of agreement ⁽⁶²⁾. Whilst this approach is commonly used for assessment of validity, it is important to remember that such comparisons are reliant on assumptions of validity of the reference method, and as such caution in interpretation is always needed. Often several methods of comparison are used, and the findings combined (e.g., comparison to reference method and use of biomarkers) to support and strengthen interpretations ^(45; 49; 61).

Before use of any intake assessment tool or use of data derived from a study using the tool, researchers should consider previous validation of the tool ⁽¹⁶⁾. The researcher should be aware, not only if the tool was validated, but how validity was defined. In addition, one needs to consider which population group the tool was validated in (e.g., country, age-group) and consider if the assumptions

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within their proposed study or analysis matches the assumptions under which the tool was validated ⁽⁶³⁾. Ideally, population demographics of the validation study should be comparable to the population being investigated. The researcher should also consider if the dietary variables and portion size estimates used in the tool are comparable to their study design or analysis.

Considering the data sources behind the derivation of nutrient intakes, food databases, composition and portion size estimates used within the tool should be from a reliable, scientifically sound source (e.g., CoFID, USDA or similar). Food composition databases have been shown to be one of the most influential determinants in comparing energy and nutrient intakes among different commercial apps ⁽⁶⁴⁾, and in explaining discrepancies in apps and their reference methods across validation studies ⁽⁶⁵⁾. This is particularly important if a researcher is considering using data arising from a technology-based method, as these are often ‘user determined’ or a combination of user derived data and published datasets, thus making it difficult to determine the quality of the nutrient intake data produced ⁽⁵¹⁾. In addition, in many dietary intake apps, information is only available for a limited number of nutrients (predominantly macronutrients and calories) ⁽⁵¹⁾. Therefore dietary intake apps may be most appropriate for use by researchers assessing intake on a food level or assessing food choice and preferences, yet may not be of sufficient quality for use by researchers interested in specific nutrient intakes ⁽⁵¹⁾. To assist researchers in selecting an appropriate assessment tool for their study, Best Practice Guidelines have been established ⁽¹⁶⁾, some of the principles applied in this can also be considered when utilising data arising from the use of these tools.

Factors which influence quality in data collection

In addition to the tool / method to collect intake data, one must also consider the context and conditions during data collection. If an interviewer-led method of data collection is being used such as a 24-hour recall or diet history, all researchers should be trained in that method to ensure they have the appropriate skills to minimise recall bias and to ensure the highest quality of information is obtained ^(36; 66). The length and timing of data collection must also be considered, for example collection of data across multiple days is suggested to increase the overall data quality, where nutrient intakes can be calculated as a daily average, giving a more accurate representation of an individual’s diet ⁽¹⁶⁾. Consideration should also be given to the days of the week that are collected ^(67; 68). Often an individual’s diet varies between weekdays and weekend days thus many studies aim to collect across the week, with proportionate amounts of week and weekend days, either at an individual (where each person has both weekend and weekday data) or at a population level (where across the full dataset there are proportionate amounts of week and weekend days ^(16; 47)). Whilst having multiple days is considered important to address day to day variation, increasing the length of measurement is not

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always ideal, as it is reported to impact on user engagement, and alterations in habitual diet. However, although repeated measurements may cause some individual's to consciously or sub-consciously alter their diet, overall repeated measurements increases the overall data quality ⁽³⁶⁾. Regardless of the method chosen, reactive bias exists in both traditional and technology-based methods, where participants are likely to adjust or misreport real food consumption due to social desirability ^(16; 69). The unintentional omissions of discretionary ingredients such as, for example, table salt and milk in tea, is found in both methods thus underlying the importance of having trained researchers in interviewer-led methods or automatic prompts in tools to minimise this ⁽⁷⁰⁾.

Alongside interview and diary methods, the length of time the data collection process takes can also influence other methods of assessment including FFQs, which can take up to 45 minutes to complete ⁽⁷¹⁾. The incorporation of technology could improve the balance between detail capturing and length of completing the recording (probing questions, image recordings, etc.).

Finally, while considering reporting of food intake, one must closely consider the method of determining portion size data. Portion size estimation can be derived from a number of methods including weighing of food, portion size photos, household measures and assignment of average portion weight from existing datasets ^(36; 72; 73). The approach to collection of portion size data varies with each method and study, so it is important to understand how portion size data is derived, and the errors associated with the approach used. For example, portion size estimation has been found to be the main contributor for dietary underreporting for 24-hour recalls ^(74; 75), and some FFQs do not ascertain portion size at all, simply assigning a previously published average portion size to each food item listed ⁽⁷⁶⁾. More recently, as online tools incorporate images of multiple portion sizes this error may be reduced, however these methods still rely on the participant to remember and identify the correct portion size of the food consumed. Most recently, much work has focused on image analysis of portion size, which has the potential to overcome current limitations with respect to portion size and food data collection, however current advances are still lacking in detail and accuracy for widespread use ⁽⁷⁷⁾. As this technology progresses, aspects of quality in data collection remain the same – identification of food, quantification of portion size, and correct use of food composition data to translate to nutrient intakes.

3.4 Maintaining quality standards when handling dietary intake data

Identification and handling of dietary under- and over-reporters

Once dietary intake data is collected and translated into nutrient intakes, several aspects of the data are important to consider before using the data in analysis. Outside of the usual examination of normal distributions, and outliers, it is important to consider the subjective nature of dietary intake, and the impact reporting one's intake has on an individual's food choice / food related behaviour. One key area is the issue of under-reporting⁽⁶⁹⁾. Under-reporting refers to specific errors in reported dietary intake, which is often identified by comparison of reported energy intake to a biomarker and/or reference method for measuring or estimating energy expenditure, with those reporting a mean energy intake below a specific limit, compared to the reference method or biomarker, designated as under reporters⁽⁶⁹⁾. There are several methods for identifying under reporters, but irrespective of the method or tool being used, underreporting is a concern for all dietary data collection methods, with levels of under-reporting typically ranging from 18 to 54% of the whole sample, but can be as high as 70% in particular subgroups⁽⁶⁹⁾. Factors influencing under-reporting in 24-hour recalls include knowledge, memory and interview situation, while for dietary records factors mostly related to reactivity bias associated with demographic or psychological indices⁽⁶⁹⁾. Whilst much of the focus is on identification of under reporters, conversely, dietary over-reporting can also affect the quality of dietary intake data⁽⁷⁸⁾. The approach to identify over-reporters is less uniform, usually individuals who are above a specific upper limit (e.g., 5000kcal/day), set by the researchers involved in data collection or analysis, are designated as 'over-reporters'. Again, inclusion and exclusion of this cohort is dependent on specific analysis and research question being considered⁽⁷⁹⁾. Once identified, inclusion or exclusion of individuals, identified as mis reporters (under or over-reporters), in subsequent analysis is dependent on the questions being considered. In order to manage the effect of misreporting, researchers frequently complete their analysis on the total population and then repeat the analysis excluding dietary mis reporters, using adequate reporters only, to assess the effect misreporting may or may not be having on the study results⁽⁸⁰⁾.

Use of standardised or local food classifying coding systems

The manner in which we handled data around food intake with respect to coding is an important point of discussion. Food intake is first collected through the description(s) of food(s) consumed using common facets/descriptors (e.g., source, packaging, etc.). Based on the descriptions provided/selected, food codes are allocated either automatically in a tool/system, or manually by trained personnel⁽³⁰⁾. Once a food code is assigned, the accompanying food composition for the food

from a designated food composition database is assigned and used to determine nutrient intakes ⁽²⁰⁾. Use of standardised food classification systems (such as Foodex2) or detailed descriptions of the food items within a dietary intake dataset are important for accurate identification, and correct allocation of appropriate composition ⁽⁸¹⁾. In recent years, use of Foodex2 has overtaken LanguaL to become the most commonly used classification system; however, LanguaL is still used within those working in food composition. In addition, the use of common or standardised coding systems can facilitate the mapping and merging of data from different datasets and allow accurate comparisons of nutritional statuses between different countries ⁽⁸²⁾. Two of the most commonly used, at this point are LanguaL and FoodEx2 ^(83; 84). LanguaL is a multilingual thesaural system using faceted classification for describing, capturing and retrieving data about food. The thesaurus provides a standardised language for describing foods, specifically for classifying food products for information retrieval. FoodEx2 is a comprehensive and flexible food classification and description system developed by EFSA to support exposure assessment and data collection and exchange in different food safety-related domains.

3.5 Use and analysis of dietary intake data

At an over-arching level, analysis of food intake data can be considered at 4 different levels; nutrients, foods/food groups ⁽⁸⁵⁾, dietary patterns ⁽⁸⁶⁾ and meal patterns ⁽⁸⁷⁾. The types of analysis capable of being carried out on the data collected using the different assessment methods are summarised in Table 3. Irrespective of whether a traditional or technology-based method is used to collect dietary intake data the analytical potential of the data is the same.

Nutrients

The simplest approach to assessing dietary intake data is determination of nutrient intakes from food items, and diets consumed. Basic statistical analysis can identify mean, macronutrient and micronutrient intakes among individuals and cohort groups. This can be completed in 2 different ways, in absolute amounts consumed and as a proportion of energy intake (% energy from food, or amount per 10MJ) to allow more direct comparisons across specific population groups (e.g., sex) ⁽⁸⁵⁾. Reported nutrient intakes can be directly compared to population reference nutrient guidelines. Assessment of nutrient intake is especially important when identifying risks of sub-optimal or deficient supply of specific nutrients in a given population or individual.

Foods/Food Groups

Determination of food group intakes is often used when interpreting dietary intake data within a population. Analysis of food group intakes allow researchers to determine the main food sources of nutrients and identify the quality of a population's nutrient intakes or overall diet. Food group intake is also assessed when examining mean intakes of food items among population groups. Such data can be used to support the development of national food reformulation strategies, and to update food based dietary guidelines. However, moving from individual foods to food groups requires aggregation of specific food items into these groups. Such food group classification systems are not universally standardised across national surveys or research groups, which often makes comparisons and interpretation of this data complex and challenging. Several food coding systems are available (e.g., LanguaL and Foodex2) to classify food items into standardised food groups and categories, and allow direct comparison of foods and food groups across appropriately coded datasets ^(88; 89).

Dietary and Meal Patterns

Dietary pattern analysis moves away from single nutrients or food/food groups and allows for the synergistic nature of dietary intake to be considered ⁽⁹⁰⁾. Dietary patterns can be analysed using priori or posteriori approaches, working to understand the relationship between dietary intake and health. The priori approach helps determine how intakes relate to dietary recommendations and examples include dietary index scores such as the Healthy Eating Index (HEI) and Mediterranean Diet Score (MDS), which allow researchers to assess dietary habits and quality on an individual and population level ⁽⁹¹⁾. A posteriori approach involves statistical modelling of dietary data through techniques such as factor or cluster analysis ^(92; 93). An advantage of the posteriori approach is that it assesses multiple aspects of dietary intake, not just specific food groups as the case with the priori approach ⁽⁹⁴⁾. Meal pattern analysis builds on the complexity of dietary pattern analysis, and aims to examine not just the combination of foods/nutrients in a given individuals (dietary pattern) but also how and when foods are combined at specific meals or times across a given period, typically a day. Analysis of meal patterns can use differing statistical techniques to identify meal in different ways: temporal, content and context patterns ⁽⁹⁵⁾. Like the examination of food and nutrient intakes and dietary patterns, the use of meal pattern analysis can examine links to disease risk and aims to improve the provision of dietary advice and enhance existing food-based dietary guidelines, with practical benefits for individuals relating to meal planning and preparation ⁽⁹⁵⁾. When undertaking analysis of dietary and meal patterns consideration should be given to the type of data being used, data derived from limited days of dietary intake are not appropriate for calculating usual dietary quality, due to the amount of day-to-day variation ⁽⁹⁶⁾.

Risk assessment

Dietary intake data can also be used to identify food intake related exposure to chemicals and associated health impacts. Food additives are natural or synthetic chemicals added *intentionally* to food to prevent it from spoiling, preserve its flavour, enhance its texture or appearance or to fulfil specific technological (e.g., organoleptic) functions & safety requirements ⁽⁹⁷⁾. Next to food additives, a variety of chemicals potentially harmful for human health can be *unintentionally* present in/on food as a result of food production, processing, packaging or transport processes as well as of environmental contamination ⁽⁹⁸⁾. Even though food additives undergo rigorous safety testing and are controlled by strict laws, a variety of food additives have been linked to multiple health issues including asthma or other allergies, depression, hyperactivity and learning disabilities in children and migraine headaches ⁽⁹⁹⁾; Groten et al., 2000; Lessof, 1995; Murray, 2020; Simon, 2003). Therefore, assessing the risk contaminants pose to populations/population sub-groups is of interest to public health policy makers, health researchers, consumers and food regulation agencies.

Table 3.2: Quality Considerations for Collection / Handling / Analysis of Dietary Intake Assessment- description of key markers / details to assess quality and use of data

Data Collection	Data Management	Data Analysis
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Validated tool ● Timeframe ● Population ● Interviewer-led or self-administered ● Prospective or retrospective 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Coding- any strategy used e.g., Foodex2 or local/national system ● Food composition linkage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Correction for measurement errors ● Energy adjustment ● Nutrient proportion of energy intake ● Handling- under reporting considered, data checked

Table 3.3: Analytical potential of data- Types of data collected from tools/methods, description of the type of analysis suitable for each tool(s)/ method – link to example papers / description of methods.

Methodology	Nutrients	Foods/food groups	Dietary Patterns	Meal Patterns
24-hour Dietary Recall	✓	✓	✓	✓
Food frequency questionnaire (FFQ)	✓	✓	✓	X
Food diary	✓	✓	✓	✓
Diet history	✓	✓	✓	?*

* Dependent on the level of detail collected

4 Consumer behaviour data

4.1 What is consumer behaviour data?

Consumer behaviour research addresses the understanding of human behaviour relating to the purchase and consumption of economic goods ⁽¹⁰⁰⁾. Jacoby defines consumer behaviour as the “acquisition, consumption and disposition of products, services, time and ideas by decision making units” ⁽¹⁰¹⁾. Research in this area strives to understand associated consumer choices and related cognitive and emotional processes. It finds application in the fields of (social) marketing and policy making (e.g., effect of taxing on the demand for sugar sweetened beverages). Research into consumer behaviour can be applied across two different, though complementary scientific disciplines: economics and psychosocial sciences. From an economic point of view, consumer behaviour is the result of choices ⁽¹⁰²⁾. Choices are typically made based on limited information regarding prices, product quality and related utility. From a psychosocial point of view, human behaviour in general is related to several constructs such as motives, attitudes, and intentions, and the same holds true for consumer behaviour or eating behaviour in particular ^(102; 103).

Within the realm of food and nutrition, the study of consumer behaviour is centred on food choice, motives for food purchasing, and perceptions of risk in relation to certain foods and new food technologies. Consumer behaviour data collection in relation to food often encompasses collection of the following ^(103; 104; 105):

- characteristics of consumers, such as socioeconomic information (e.g., economic situation, education, household composition), classification of personality, or eating typology (e.g., stress-related eating, mindful eating)
- characteristics of food product, such as price, amount/volume, quality (e.g., from sustainable production)
- characteristics of purchasing situation such as date/time, point of sale, self-service, eating-out
- characteristics of decision process prior to purchasing, such as preferences, attitudes, motives, values, intentions, trust, or willingness to pay
- characteristics of post-consumption situation such as perceived utility, consumer satisfaction, willingness to repeat consumption.

The above information is often combined with food intake data to determine the impact of food choices and purchases on immediate or habitual food intake and can be used to support public health

and/or marketing campaigns ⁽¹⁰⁶⁾. Knowledge of consumer behaviour, and the factors influencing the same, can inform food product development, dietary health public policy and marketing strategies ⁽¹⁰⁷⁾.

4.2 Methods of collection

Typically, the collection of consumer behaviour data is led by a specific theoretical framework, for instance Utility Theory ⁽¹⁰⁸⁾ from an economic perspective or the Theory of Planned Behaviour ⁽¹⁰⁹⁾ from a psychological perspective. Methods applied within the constructs of these frameworks, see consumer behaviour data collected using interviews/focus groups, projective techniques, questionnaires, observations and agent-based modelling thus incorporating both quantitative and qualitative research methods ⁽¹¹⁰⁾.

Consumer behaviour data can be collected by a wide variety of methods, both direct and indirect. Indirect approaches, including for example consumer data from scanner cash registers, can provide detailed information regarding the type of products, but little information on the consumers or the decision process underlying the act of purchasing. Direct approaches require more detailed involvement of the respective consumers, with methods ranging from pure observation (e.g., selection of foods/drinks at buffets), to interviews, questionnaires or diaries ⁽¹¹⁰⁾. The selection of the method will depend on various factors including the research question, the type of consumer data being collected (behaviour data such as purchasing behaviour or opinion data such as food choice) ⁽¹⁰²⁾. Specific methods of collection are considered below and summarised in Table 4.1.

Interviews

Interviews can follow a structured or unstructured approach whereby the former involves a set list of questions to be asked whilst the latter allows the researcher freedom to explore the interview topics in any order and to probe as little or as much as they desire into different topics ⁽¹¹⁰⁾. Advantages of structured interviews include all participants responses are easily comparable and the responses are easily quantifiable ⁽¹¹⁰⁾. Conversely, some participants may feel excluded from the research if their opinions aren't captured in the answer options ⁽¹¹⁰⁾. Furthermore, interviews can be costly and time consuming, requiring consideration of time, remuneration, transcription and data coding/manipulation ⁽¹¹⁰⁾.

Projective techniques

Projective techniques “provide verbal or visual stimuli which, through their indirection and concealed intent, encourage respondents to reveal their unconscious feelings and attitudes without being aware that they are doing so” ⁽¹¹¹⁾. This enables researchers to explore people’s thoughts, feelings, and experiences and can help participants to talk about private motivations without feeling pressured to answer direct questions. As participants are unaware what the real intentions of the study/interactions are, they are subsequently less likely to provide socially desirable responses ⁽¹¹⁰⁾. Similar to unstructured interviews, responses from projective techniques may be more challenging to compare as they do not tend to follow a uniform approach ⁽¹¹⁰⁾. There is often variation in the stimuli provided, the population the research is carried out in, and the themes (opinions, emotions and experiences) expressed by participants.

Questionnaires

Questionnaires are a fast, cost-effective approach to collecting data from large number of participants ⁽¹¹⁰⁾. They are most effective when the structure is simple, and the questions are to the point. Unlike other methods of collecting consumer behaviour data, questionnaire-based data is quantitative in nature therefore data is easily comparable between different population groups (even across various countries). Whilst the data arising from questionnaires is quantitative, often the development of questionnaires arises from qualitative research, whereby qualitative, exploratory research such as focus groups or interviews are first conducted to provide information which can inform the development of a specific questionnaire. This, in turn is usually validated before deployment. Questionnaires are frequently used to collect data on food choice ⁽¹⁰⁷⁾.

Observations

Collection of consumer behaviour data through observations includes watching (recording) individuals’ behaviours, events, and noting physical characteristics within their natural settings ⁽¹¹⁰⁾. This method removes the self-reported element from participants thus removing recall bias and memory issues which are often major sources of error in market research ⁽¹¹⁰⁾. A structured checklist including details of the specific behaviours to be observed and details of the time, location and setting is often used ⁽¹¹⁰⁾. While advantages do exist, disadvantages or criticisms are centred on its ‘closed’ approach whereby only pre-specified behaviours are observed meaning other behaviours which may not have been previously identified could be ignored ⁽¹¹⁰⁾. Furthermore, the method only focuses on identifying whether a pre-specified behaviour is present or absent ⁽¹¹⁰⁾. Detailed descriptions of the behaviour or further contextual information is often not collected using this method, so thus it is most appropriate for collection of behaviours which are easy to identify and describe ⁽¹¹⁰⁾. This method can be useful for behaviours which participants may be likely to change if they were aware they were

under observation (usually addressed as Hawthorne effect) ⁽¹¹⁰⁾. From an ethical point of view, however, any observation would require an informed consent from the respective subjects, which obviously conflicts with the aim of avoiding the Hawthorne effect while collecting information from the subjects.

Table 4.1: Summary of methods for collecting consumer behaviour data

Methodology	Description	Advantages	Disadvantages	Appropriate Use
Interviews	A conversation with prepared questions or pre-defined topics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can obtain detailed information about personal feelings, perceptions, and opinions • Allows for detailed questions which usually achieve a high response rate • Researcher can ensure all questions are fully answered 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time consuming • Expensive • Not feasible for large numbers • Different interviewers may understand and transcribe interviews in different ways. 	
Projective techniques	provide verbal or visual stimuli which, through their indirection and concealed intent, encourage respondents to reveal their unconscious feelings and attitudes without being aware that they are doing so	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • may elicit responses that subjects would be unwilling or unable to give if they knew the purpose of the study • Useful for addressing personal or sensitive topics, or that where social desirability may be at play. • Useful when underlying motivations, beliefs, and attitudes are operating at a subconscious level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Require highly trained interviewers • Trained interpreters required to analyse the responses • Risk of interpretation bias • Costly • May require respondents to engage in unusual behaviour • Participant selected may not be representative of the entire population. 	When addressing personal / sensitive topics
Questionnaires	List of questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • standardized information that is straightforward to analyse • Can quickly collect data from a large sample size • results are comparable with similar surveys used elsewhere • Participants can answer anonymously, which may produce more honest answers • Online questionnaires are cost effective 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subject to participants misinterpreting questions • Must collect reasonable sample size in order to say responses represent the whole population • Response rates can be poor. • Designing, producing, distributing, and analysing the questionnaires may make them expensive and time consuming 	When assessing attitudes, opinions, beliefs or perceptions

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			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Produces quantitative data which may not be enough to answer the research questions 	
Observation	Collection of data by watching behaviours, events, or noting physical characteristics within their natural settings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quick and easy to administer • Doesn't require researcher training • Several observers can gather the same information to check for reliability • Can collect information on many behaviours simultaneously 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Closed" method, can only observe what is stated in the checklist • Limited to "presence" or "absence" of specified behaviour • Lack of information about the quality and duration of behaviour and a description • Expensive data to. The observer must wait, doing nothing, between observation events. 	For consumer behaviours that are easy to describe in a logical order or which participants may change if they were aware they were being studied e.g., shopping habits

Household budget surveys

From a societal and economic perspective, consumer behaviour data are typically derived from household budget surveys (HBS), which are conducted in an internationally standardised way by national statistical offices in country-representative samples ^(112; 113). Participating households are requested to record their food acquisition (often referred to as food availability on household level) for a period of two or more weeks. With respect to foods and beverages, the collected data comprise purchases, contributions from own production (e.g., from gardens) and items offered to household members gratuitously, e.g., as gifts. Advantages of this method include the fact that they often use representative samples of households, generate a significant amount of nutrition data, and allow for simultaneous collection of socio-demographic data ⁽¹¹³⁾. However, there are also several limitations associated with this method. HBS nutrition data can differ between countries and eating-out is only assessed monetarily without specification of the types of foods or dishes consumed ⁽¹¹⁴⁾. The data are typically collected over a period of twelve months applying a rolling procedure in order to capture seasonal variation.

Consumer experiments

From a psychological perspective, the collection of consumer behaviour data applies standardised and validated psychometric tools focusing on specific aspects of consumer behaviour. The Salzburg Stress Eating Scale (SSES), for instance, assesses consumers' dietary response to stressful situations and the tendency to indulge in comfort foods ⁽¹¹⁵⁾. The Eating Motivation Survey (TEMS) considers fifteen distinct motivations related to food choices ⁽¹¹⁶⁾. Other tools measure consumers' trust in food chain actors ⁽¹¹⁷⁾; and the list could be continued over pages and volumes. An important aspect of consumer behaviour, for both economic and public health strategies, is the assessment of willingness to pay. It has been shown that consumers' responses to direct questions are poorly reliable and prone to biases from social desirability. Therefore, willingness-to-pay is typically measured indirectly using various types of choice experiments and conjoint analyses, where consumers' preferences are broken down to various product attributes.

Novel methods of collecting consumer behaviour data

As technology has advanced in recent decades, new forms of data have become available, which have enabled further exploration of consumer choice and behaviours ⁽¹⁰²⁾. Although, still in their relative infancy in comparison to the previously described methods, novel methods of collecting consumer behaviour data including collection of data from consumer credit cards or store loyalty cards; through (unintentional) tracking by mobile phones; use of Smart Glasses ⁽¹¹⁸⁾; and, big data are likely to be

further exploited for collection of consumer behaviour data in future. Big data comprises three main areas, social data, machine data and transactional data and are used in marketing to analyse data points of a customer's journey from exploration to sale.

Collection of consumer behaviour data via these methods raises concerns over consumer data protection, privacy issues and also, the quality of the resulting data ⁽¹¹⁹⁾. Questions are raised over the management of collected big data with substantial 'data cleaning' likely required before analysis could be completed ⁽¹¹⁹⁾. Furthermore, the data may be lacking scientific rigour in terms of sample representativeness, not collecting a complete set of the required variables, uncertainty over how long the data will be available, and the timeframe of when the data was collected among other potential issues ⁽¹¹⁹⁾.

4.3 Quality considerations in the collection of consumer behaviour data

Quality of consumer behaviour data needs to be considered on several levels, each of which can influence the use and quality of the data generated, these are tool(s) (e.g., questionnaire, data source), population and context / food(s) considered in the analysis.

Method

It is important that the correct data collection method is chosen for the desired type of consumer data to be studied. If behaviours are the focus of interest, observations are an appropriate method whilst focus groups, interviews and questionnaires are more appropriate for the study of consumer mental processes involved in their decision making including emotions, opinions, perceptions, beliefs and attitudes ⁽¹⁰²⁾. Most methods of collecting consumer behaviour data are qualitative, thus quality is dependent on how well the study has been designed and whether the appropriate methodology has been selected to capture the desired consumer behaviour.

Population

In an ideal world, consumer behaviour datasets would include population representative samples, with detailed demographic characteristics including financial status and educational data. Alongside this detailed food purchase data, collection of consumption location could ideally be included ⁽¹²⁰⁾. This ideal gives a summary outline of important quality issues associated with consumer data. The population examined, both size and characteristics, will determine the scope and interpretation of any analysis which can be conducted on any given dataset ⁽¹⁰²⁾. For example, to examine factors influencing

food choice of a population, data would cover the total population or a representative sample of considerable size (and free of any selection bias), suited to or directed by the research question being considered ⁽¹²¹⁾. Once the population is determined, the information or variables collected on the cohort, will also influence any datasets use and applicability, and would most commonly include detailed information on the sociodemographic as well as psychosocial characteristics of the consumers available (e.g., age, gender/sex, education, eating motives, values, dietary regime). Additionally, the time range of data collection would cover seasonal variation in food intake and choices, as this has been shown previously to influence food choice and purchasing ⁽¹²²⁾. Timing of cultural influences, such as festivities and celebrations also need to be considered with respect to their influence on the findings ⁽¹²³⁾.

When using focus groups as a collection method, particular consideration should be given to the selected population to ensure the data collected is of a high quality ⁽¹⁰²⁾. Firstly, participants should be recruited based on their knowledge on the topic of interest ⁽¹⁰²⁾. Consideration should also be given to the combinations of participants included in a single focus group, for example, if there are power differences between participants this may dissuade some participants from sharing their thoughts or may encourage all participants to simply agree with a participant ⁽¹⁰²⁾. The researcher moderating the focus group should have received appropriate training in qualitative methodology and sufficient time and thought should have gone into the development of the topic guide prior to beginning the focus groups ⁽¹⁰²⁾.

Context

Consumer behaviour related to food has added complexity in that food is chosen and consumed at various levels and locations and can be an individual choice or part of a complex group dynamic e.g., family or support group. Food choice is known to be affected by occupation, income and work stress thus data on these aspects are important complementary information to be collected ⁽¹²⁴⁾. Since consumption often takes place in the context of a household and its members rather than purely individualistic, data on consumers' household background would need to be included (e.g., household composition, household income) in any comprehensive dataset. With respect to the act of consumption per se, information should be available with respect to place of acquisition (preferably given as GPS coordinates), the kind of store (e.g., grocery/retail, restaurant, street-food outlet), and the time span of purchasing. Furthermore, the data would be complete in the sense of comprising all products acquired during the period of investigation and all types of product acquisition (purchases, own production, gifts etc.). Ideally, cross-sectional data would be available in a timely manner, and longitudinal data would be perfectly consistent and comparable over time.

Questionnaires

Questionnaires are the most common method used to capture consumer behaviour data due to the fact they are easy to administer, interpret, allow for the measurement of multiple variables and collection of other complementary data (e.g., demographic, lifestyle, health) ⁽¹⁰²⁾. Limitations of using cross-sectional questionnaires are the introduction of common method bias whereby variations in responses are caused by the instrument itself and social desirability where respondents may alter their responses to correspond to social norms ⁽¹⁰²⁾. Administration of longitudinal questionnaires can help overcome these biases and improve the quality of the resultant data. Use of mixed design studies that allow for further validation and external validity of the research findings may also improve the quality of the consumer behaviour data collected using questionnaires ⁽¹⁰²⁾.

Food choice data is typically collected using questionnaires ⁽¹⁰⁷⁾. As with all questionnaires it is important that they are tested for validity and reliability to ensure that they are appropriate for use in a given population group or country ⁽¹⁰⁷⁾. Food choice is typically the product of a complex mix of preferences for sensory characteristics, combined with the influence of non-sensory factors such as food-related expectations and attitudes, health claims, price, ethical concerns and mood ⁽¹⁰⁵⁾. Whilst the original food choice questionnaire was developed and tested in the UK ⁽¹²⁵⁾ it has been extensively used in many different countries often with modifications to the original questionnaire ⁽¹⁰⁷⁾. Examples of food choice questionnaire facets included in different validation studies are displayed in Table 4.2. Although these questionnaires are highly similar, the use of additional facets in some food choice questionnaires would limit its comparability with other countries.

Table 4.2: Variation in food choice questionnaires and additional study variables analysed*

Food Choice Questionnaire	Country	Survey type	Factors assessed	Other study variables
Traditional 8 factor FCQ, with additional 29 items ⁽¹²⁶⁾	USA	Web-based	Health, mood, convenience, sensory appeal, natural content, price, weight control, familiarity, ethical concern, impression management, food safety	Relation of regulatory focus and food choice motives
Traditional 8 factor FCQ (excluding mood factor)	Belgium, France, Italy, Norway, Poland, Spain	Web-based	weight control, price, ethical concern, convenience, natural content, health, sensory appeal, and familiarity	Subjective health, attitude and consumption of traditional food
Traditional 8 factor FCQ ⁽¹²⁷⁾	Croatia, Bosnia, Macedonia, Slovenia, Serbia, Montenegro	Face-to-face interviews	Health, mood, convenience, sensory appeal, natural content, price, weight control, familiarity	Factors underlying food choice
Traditional 8 factor FCQ ⁽¹²⁸⁾ including ethical concern	Belgium, Hungary, Romania, Philippines	On-screen computer application	Health, mood, convenience, sensory appeal, natural content, price, weight control, familiarity, ethical concern	Mean importance and rank of food choice factors
Traditional 8 factor FCQ ⁽¹²⁹⁾	Greece	Self-administered	Health, mood, convenience, sensory appeal, natural content, price, weight control, familiarity	

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Traditional 8 factor FCQ with additional 3 factors ⁽¹³⁰⁾	Russia	Face-to-face interviews	Health, mood, convenience, sensory appeal, natural content, price, weight control, familiarity, animal welfare, political values, religion items	Food choice motives
Modified 7 factor FCQ ⁽¹³¹⁾	Uruguay	Paper based	Health and nutritional value, sensory appeal, weight control, familiarity, price and convenience, feeling good and safety, natural content	Food choice motives, age and gender influence on willingness to try functional foods
Traditional 8 factor FCQ (including ethical concern) ⁽¹³²⁾	Canada, Belgium, Italy	Paper based	Health and natural content (loaded as a single factor), mood, convenience, sensory appeal, price, weight control, familiarity, ethical concern	
Traditional 8 factor FCQ (including ethical concern) ⁽¹⁰⁵⁾	Japan, Taiwan, Malaysia, New Zealand	On screen and paper based	Health, mood, convenience, sensory appeal, natural content, price, weight control, familiarity	Food choice factors differences by country, age, food neophobia

*Adapted from Markovina et al., 2015 ⁽¹⁰⁷⁾

4.4 Use and analysis of consumer behaviour data

Consumer behaviour data can be used to evaluate the impact of food choices and purchases on food intake, the effect of the food environment on health and disease developments ⁽¹⁰³⁾, to support public policies and/or marketing strategies, and to inform food behaviour interventions.

Consumer behaviour data from HBS are traditionally used for nutrition monitoring, making a considerable pillar in national and international nutrition reports. The German Nutrition Report, for instance, has been relying on HBS since its first edition in 1969, and similar approaches can be found in Brazil ⁽¹³³⁾, Ireland ⁽¹³⁴⁾, and many other European countries ⁽¹³⁵⁾. The pan-European DAFNE initiative developed a database of harmonized HBS data that allows cross-sectional as well as longitudinal analyses of food consumption and exploratory analyses of the effect of socio-economic determinants on dietary choices in more than ten different countries ⁽¹³⁶⁾. Respective results were integrated in the European Nutrition and Health Report 2009 (Food Availability at the Household Level in the European Union ⁽¹³⁷⁾). However, a general challenge of using HBS data for the purpose of nutrition monitoring is the fact that data are collected on the household level such that the allocation of consumption to individual household members is unknown (unless single-person households are considered). In order to overcome this shortcoming, statistical models were suggested ⁽¹³⁸⁾ and further refined ⁽¹³⁹⁾ that estimate food consumption of individuals based on household related information.

Data on consumer expenses for food can be used in econometrics investigating consumers' demand with respect to prices and income by applying demand models such as Deaton's Almost Ideal Demand System (AIDS) ⁽¹⁴⁰⁾. Such models yield information on consumers' price elasticities, i.e., consumers sensitivity to changes in prices. These responses may refer to the price of the considered product itself (own-price elasticity) or to those of products that could be used as substitutes (cross-price elasticity). Muhamad et al. showed for instance that globally own-price elasticities for sugar sweetened beverages (SSB) range from about -0.7 to -1.9, which means that an increase in price by 1% would lead to a reduction in demand by 0.7% to 1.9% ⁽¹⁴¹⁾. These analyses indicate the potential effects that could be expected from introducing taxes on certain products (such as SSB) or the other way round- what level of tax would be necessary to produce significant changes in demand. Furthermore, such analyses reveal potential undesired side effects of taxes on SSB on the demand for other foods and beverages. Quirnbach et al. found that taxes on SSB might decrease relative prices of alcoholic beverages such as lager, cider or wines and increase their demand respectively ⁽¹⁴²⁾.

5 Demographic and Lifestyle data

5.1 Introduction to demographic and lifestyle data

Demographics describe the characteristics of a population based on different factors such as age, sex, ethnicity, education, income, and location ⁽¹⁴³⁾. Lifestyle behaviour impacts on physical and mental health, thus affecting quality of life and risk of disease ^(144; 145). Surveys that assess general lifestyle behaviour typically cover a broad area that often includes physical activity levels, sedentary behaviour, substance use (e.g., tobacco and alcohol), dietary habits, and general health. Other factors may also be included, such as self-reported dental health, medication use, drug use, sleep habits, mental health, stress and social activities, among others ^(10; 146; 147). Both demographics and lifestyle data are collected to gain an understanding of those who are participating in research and in turn, determine whether the study results can be generalised to the target population ⁽¹⁴⁸⁾. These data are collected to define the population characteristics (knowledge of which is important in epidemiology studies), or to stratify the group for analysis (e.g., men vs women).

5.2 Methods of collecting Demographic and lifestyle data

In general, demographic and lifestyle data can be collected using interviews, questionnaires and more recently individual tracking devices, such as those monitoring physical activity and sleep. Surveys can be administered by face-to-face interviews, telephone interviews and electronically distributed (e.g., web-based surveys and tablet/smartphone apps). For large population studies, self-completed postal questionnaires are often used, however electronic surveys are becoming increasingly popular with their scalability, cost-effectiveness and efficient data collection, which reduces the risk of data loss and mistakes, however further research is needed to fully assess the impact of electronic surveys on data quality and cost-efficiency ⁽¹⁴⁹⁾.

Whether paper-based or electronically distributed, surveys and questionnaires are the most common methods of collecting demographic and lifestyle data, and although both are widely collected in research, there is a lack of standardised questionnaires for use among researchers with a wide variety of tools which can be utilised ⁽¹⁵⁰⁾. One example of a validated tool is the General Lifestyle Questionnaire, which measures cognitive activities, physical activities, social/leisure activities, sleep habits, dietary habits, and tobacco/alcohol use, all of which are associated with health ⁽¹⁴⁶⁾, however many more validated and unvalidated tools exist. Despite there being common questions typically asked in a demographic or general lifestyle survey, these questions frequently differ in the wording

and terminology used, response options vary (e.g., pre-defined options, free text boxes), and their location within the survey can differ, all influencing participant response rates ^(151; 152). However, the scope and type of information collected is often relatively comparable across collections method.

One important aspect of lifestyle, particularly relevant to food and nutrition research, is assessment of activity. To assess levels of physical activity or sedentary behaviour (characterised by low energy expenditure activities (≤ 1.5 metabolic equivalents) that an individual performs when awake ^(153; 154)), there are multiple subjective measures ⁽¹⁵³⁾. Comprehensive lists of physical activity questionnaires (PAQ), sedentary behaviour questionnaires (SBQ) have previously been published ^(153; 155). There are also emerging Web and smartphone applications, such as BeWell24 and ACT24, that self-monitor sleep and different activities over 24 hours to determine sedentary behaviour and activity levels ^(156; 157), as well as online 24 h physical activity recall tools ⁽¹⁵⁸⁾. Growing in popularity over the last decade are devices to objectively assess PAL, including wearable activity monitors (e.g., accelerometers), pedometers, heart rate monitors, multi-sensors (e.g., accelerometers with heart rate monitors) and GPS units, although none are considered the gold-standard ⁽¹⁵⁹⁾. Sedentary behaviour can be assessed using thigh-worn inclinometer devices (sometimes incorporated into accelerometers) that monitor posture (e.g., activPAL, widely considered the gold-standard) ^(160; 161). Commercial activity trackers such as FitBit and Garmin are not designed for research for a variety of reasons including the fact algorithms can change when users update their devices, third-party sites manage the data and higher rates of data loss are reported. Despite this, they have been used successfully in numerous studies ⁽¹⁶²⁾.

Sleep measurement

With advancing technology, measurement of sleep has become a new area of lifestyle data collection. Sleep can be captured by wearable fitness watches / devices and can generate various measurements of sleep, e.g., total sleep length, sleep quality and stages of sleep. Advantages of collecting sleep measurements through use of wearable fitness devices include its cost efficiency, ability to easily obtain longitudinal data and that participants sleep is measured in their normal, free-living environment ^(163; 164). However, it must be noted that this technology is still relatively new and the quality of the data arising from these devices is variable ⁽¹⁶³⁾. Certain models may overestimate total sleep time and sleep efficiency, and underestimate wake after sleep onset. More recent models that incorporate both heart rate variability and body movement to assess sleep stages show improved accuracy ⁽¹⁶³⁾. These devices are likely to improve and become more accurate in the near future.

5.3 Quality considerations when collecting demographic and lifestyle data

Population Response Rates

Although surveys (questionnaires) are most frequently used for collecting large scale demographic and lifestyle data, they are time-consuming to input and quality check ⁽¹⁴⁹⁾, and there are concerns about declining response rates ⁽¹⁴⁷⁾. Certain population groups are more prone to not responding such as younger men or those with poorer health, than other groups, which can cast doubt on the reliability of data if such considerations are not addressed through population weighting or other techniques ^(165; 166; 167). In a recent example, lifestyle questionnaires were posted to 5000 Finnish working adults and non-responders received a follow-up telephone interview ⁽¹⁶⁸⁾. Compared with postal respondents (who were typically older and female), telephone respondents were more likely to be smokers, with women also tending to be heavy episodic drinkers with poorer self-reported fitness levels ⁽¹⁶⁸⁾. Furthermore to ensure representation of the population, it has been suggested that postal surveys should be supplemented with interviews for some ethnic minority groups, for example, where illiteracy and language barriers exist, or translated versions of the questionnaire should be available ⁽¹⁴⁷⁾. Electronic, as opposed to postal, surveys are growing in popularity, however, they may exclude individuals who are not technology literate and do not have internet/smartphone access ⁽¹⁶⁹⁾. Therefore, to ensure quality, it is important that the choice of survey method suits the specific target population and follow-up with an alternative method may be necessary to help eliminate selection bias and boost response rates ⁽³⁶⁾.

Response rates to individual demographic questions can vary considerably and this variation needs to be considered independently of overall population or study response rate. This is particularly important in relation to questions that are considered 'sensitive', such as sexual orientation, gender identity, and ethnicity. These are reported as more likely to receive "prefer not to say" or missing responses, providing an inaccurate representation of the cohort sample ^(170; 171). Responses to questions related to these topics across differing groups vary, with more marginalised groups often selecting 'prefer not to say' meaning data on specific groups can be disproportionality lacking ^{(170) (171; 172)}. The use of pre-defined responses can also lead to unwanted effects, such as participant drop out and the collection of broad demographic data ⁽¹⁵¹⁾. When asking about gender or other sensitive questions, open-ended questions are recommended so participants can use terms they feel are most appropriate for them and give more than one response. Additionally, a list of pre-defined responses can be perceived as a researcher's order of preference, thus these should be listed in a random or alphabetical order. Knowledge of population characteristics, response rates and level of completeness

(missing values) are important to know ⁽¹⁵¹⁾ and consider when using datasets to understand how representative the population is, and how appropriate the data is for the question/analysis being considered.

Demographics

One of the key challenges in collection and use of demographic data is the variation in terminology and language used in collection. For example, certain terminology used in demographic questions is often wrongly used interchangeably, such as sex and gender ⁽¹⁷³⁾ or race and ethnicity ⁽¹⁷¹⁾. Sex is defined as the ‘biological aspects of an individual as determined by their anatomy’ and gender as ‘a social construction relating to behaviours and attributes based on labels of masculinity and femininity’ ⁽¹⁷⁴⁾. Therefore, gender identity may not match the individual’s sex at birth. Race is considered to be the biological or phenotypic characteristics of an individual, whereas ethnicity refers to the social categories, such as language and religion ⁽¹⁷⁵⁾. Therefore, these terms should be used in the correct context and defined, as responses may differ depending on the participant’s interpretation, and should be asked as two separate questions when required. In addition to the incorrect use, defined lists for use are lacking, leading to variation in the number and nomenclature of categories or groups within questionnaires, which may impact on the ability to merge and conduct combined analysis across existing multiple datasets.

The location of demographic questions within a survey is also found to be important. There are arguments for placing them at the start, when determining a participant’s eligibility ⁽¹⁷⁶⁾ and identifying trends in demographic groups who dropout before completing a study ⁽¹⁵¹⁾. In contrast, arguments for placing demographic questions at the end of surveys include presenting sensitive questions last to avoid putting people off completing the study and these are easier questions to answer when participants may be experiencing study fatigue ^(151; 152).

The method through which demographic questions are asked can also influence the quality of results. For example, previous studies have found that individuals feel more comfortable providing their information to a trusted healthcare professional rather than entering the information into a questionnaire or survey as they have the opportunity to ask questions ^(172; 177; 178). Using such approaches, it may be possible that studies could result in fewer “prefer not to say” and fewer missing responses.

Lifestyle

There are few standardised and comprehensive general lifestyle questionnaires for use in the clinical and research setting, and details of questionnaires, including their development, reliability and validation are sparse ^(146; 179). Those that exist can be lengthy (for example, the Questionnaire on Quality of Life contains 317 questions ⁽¹⁸⁰⁾) or their validity is unclear ⁽¹⁸¹⁾. Some, like the 1984 FANTASTIC lifestyle assessment ⁽¹⁸²⁾, requires updating to reflect current lifestyle habits. This is true of all lifestyle questionnaires, which should continually evolve, for example, ‘screen time’ may not feature on older questionnaires.

When choosing a lifestyle questionnaire, their purpose should be considered. Some quantify or categorise overall lifestyle behaviour. For example, the validated General Lifestyle Questionnaire gives users a score to assess their overall lifestyle ⁽¹⁴⁶⁾, whereas the FANTASTIC lifestyle assessment assigns users to one of four lifestyle behaviour categories ⁽¹⁸²⁾. Of note, both include questions on different lifestyle behaviours and different scoring methods, making comparisons difficult. Alternatively, questionnaires can focus on single aspects of lifestyle (e.g., PAL, smoking) or specific population groups (e.g., older adults). They may also be tailored to lifestyle factors associated with a specific disease/health condition ⁽¹⁷⁹⁾. It should be noted that lifestyle surveys created for one population group may not be interchangeable with other populations, thus requiring validation in different groups prior to use ⁽¹⁷⁹⁾.

Where lifestyle data is not the primary outcome of the research (e.g., if its purpose is to characterise a study sample), researchers often create their own lifestyle questions to suit their purpose, resulting in lack of consistency between studies. Moreover, these lifestyle questions are often not described in publications so they cannot be replicated easily and are often not validated. The UK’s Lifestyle Survey Toolkit also highlights that there is “no agreed national set of questions to use in local health and lifestyle surveys” and many different question variants are used ⁽¹⁸³⁾, further highlighting the need for standardisation. This will be discussed further below.

Physical activity and sedentary behaviour

Accurate quantification of physical activity levels and sedentary behaviour is difficult despite there being many questionnaires and tools for this purpose. This has been the focus of numerous systematic reviews ^(153; 154; 155; 161; 162; 184; 185; 186; 187; 188; 189; 190; 191; 192). The choice of questionnaire is important, as demonstrated by Stassen et al., where participants in an online survey each completed 4 different PAQ, however, each generated significantly different weekly volumes of moderate and vigorous intensity physical activity and the prevalence of participants meeting the recommended physical

activity targets was inconsistent, resulting in the authors calling for standardisation and harmonisation of PAQ ⁽¹⁹³⁾.

The wide range of PAQ and SBQ varies considerably. Some commonly used ones include the International Physical activity questionnaire (IPAQ), Recent Physical Activity Questionnaire (RPAQ) and Activity Questionnaire for Adults and Adolescents (AQuAA). Terwee et al. summarise the qualitative attributes of PAQs (e.g., purpose, target population), helping researchers to determine the most appropriate PAQ to use ⁽¹⁹⁴⁾. For example, the observation period can focus on the past day/week or reflect a usual week/month/year, although interpretation of 'usual' is considered confusing. Days of the week recorded are important too as there are often differences in sedentary behaviour between workdays and weekend days ⁽¹⁵³⁾. Questionnaires can be paper- or interview-based although accuracy is thought to be slightly greater for the latter ^(153; 195), and contain single or multiple questions however, single-item questionnaires appear the least reliable self-report method ^(153; 154). Since there are large numbers of PAQ that each differ slightly and lack consistency, selecting a questionnaire to use and comparing physical activity estimates between questionnaires are difficult ⁽¹⁹⁴⁾. Researchers are recommended to use and improve existing PAQ/SBQ, rather than create new versions, and choose those with sufficient content/construct validity and reliability that are appropriate for their study ⁽¹⁸⁸⁾. However, as with other lifestyle questionnaires, modifying (e.g., translating) or using an existing PAQ/SBQ in a different population group requires validation before use as quality cannot be guaranteed. A systematic review by Sember et al assessing the validity of the international PAQs recommended that "All EU countries should validate the translated PAQs in their national settings" ⁽¹⁸⁷⁾.

Despite the large numbers available, few PAQ or SBQ have acceptable validity relative to objective measures ^(155; 188), and are often subject to measurement error, which can attenuate associations between physical activity/sedentary behaviour and disease in epidemiological studies ⁽¹⁹⁶⁾. Firstly, they are prone to overestimation resulting from social desirability bias. This also has an impact on the accuracy of estimated energy expenditure ⁽¹⁹⁷⁾, which may be calculated to identify mis-reporters in dietary assessments. PAQ and SBQ rely on memory, thus they are also subject to recall bias and recall may not be suitable for older adults and children. It is thought that recall of a specific task is easier than recalling overall time spent on activities during the course of the day ⁽¹⁵⁴⁾, and the recall of more vigorous activities is more accurate than those of lower intensity ⁽¹⁹⁶⁾. Short-term recalls are recommended to reduce recall/reporting error, which was supported by a meta-analysis reporting current or previous day self-report measures of sedentary behaviour to be more accurate than usual day/week or previous week/month measures ⁽¹⁵⁴⁾. However, short-term questionnaires will be less

likely to capture infrequent and seasonal activities⁽¹⁹⁸⁾. Also, if measuring total physical activity levels, the PAQ must cover all activities (e.g., household, occupation, leisure, sports, and transport)⁽¹⁸⁸⁾. Older adults, ethnic minority groups and women typically engage more in light activities (e.g., walking, housework, gardening), which are often under-represented on PAQ^(188; 199). Questionnaires designed for specific population groups may be more appropriate to ensure quality.

Tools to objectively measure physical activity levels, such as activity monitors, have the advantage over questionnaires with respect to misreporting. Compared with doubly-labelled water, these measures are less variable when estimating energy expenditure than self-reported measures⁽¹⁸⁴⁾. Furthermore, a meta-analysis reported that self-reported methods underestimated sedentary/sitting time by 1.74 hours/day relative to device measurements⁽¹⁵⁴⁾. However, these tools are expensive to use in large-scale studies and may be subject to reactivity bias⁽¹⁵⁹⁾. When choosing an objective measure, it should be noted that not all devices perform as well as each other and they are not interchangeable. Pedometers provide less accurate step count estimates than activity monitors⁽¹⁸⁴⁾, and a meta-analysis reported lower accuracy of accelerometers at measuring sedentary behaviour than inclinometers⁽¹⁵⁴⁾. Devices also provide different outputs, pedometers simply measure steps, whereas accelerometers provide more detailed outputs, including estimated energy expenditure and minutes of activity⁽¹⁵⁹⁾. Further, some activities cannot be detected by certain devices. Accelerometers are not reliable measures of certain activities, such as weight-training, cycling, and swimming so choice of device is important. One study did not find an association between accelerometer activity counts and energy expenditure via indirect calorimetry during cycling and reported that cycling underestimated activity counts by 73% compared with walking⁽²⁰⁰⁾. Duration is also important, which appears to be somewhat dependent on device, outcome measure and population. It has been suggested that accelerometers require 2 days to generate reliable step counts in adults, increasing to 3 days for reliable estimates of total physical activity levels, whereas up to 5 days are recommended for reliable pedometer data⁽¹⁸⁴⁾. For older adults, this was slightly different, with another study recommending 3-4 days to predict total physical activity levels from both devices⁽²⁰¹⁾. Measurements also vary within devices as 1) they can be worn differently (e.g., dominant vs. non-dominant arm placement of activity trackers), 2) be worn at different times of the day, 3) use different non-wear definitions/algorithms, epoch lengths, and cut-point thresholds (which should be appropriate for the study population and device used), and 4) report different measurements (e.g., total duration vs. physical activity by intensity level vs. activity classification), all of which make comparisons between studies challenging and affect the harmonisation of data^(159; 160; 161; 162; 188). A more comprehensive summary of activity monitors, including their uses and limitations have been published by McClung et al⁽¹⁶⁰⁾.

Although they have benefits, unlike questionnaires, activity measuring devices may not provide contextual information such as distinguishing between work, transport and leisure, or detail types of activities, which is important as certain activities (e.g., time spent watching TV) are associated with poor health ⁽¹⁵³⁾. The systematic review by Dowd et al. concluded that there is no “perfect” tool to assess physical activity in adults ⁽¹⁸⁴⁾, and it has been proposed by others that assessment of physical activity or sedentary behaviour be performed using a combination of objective and subjective measures wherever possible as they provide complimentary information ^(155; 197; 199). The creation of standards for using and reporting activity monitor data have also been recommended ⁽¹⁸⁸⁾.

Smoking status

Smoking status is typically assessed via self-reported measures. There are few designated and validated questionnaires for measuring smoking status as it is often incorporated within health/lifestyle surveys, such as the UK’s General Health Survey ⁽²⁰²⁾. Systematic reviews or meta-analyses assessing the validity and reliability of current smoking questionnaires are lacking or outdated ^(203; 204). Over the past few decades, smoking has become less socially acceptable, which has contributed to an underestimation in smoking prevalence when assessed by self-report and the subsequent inaccuracy of current smoking trends ⁽²⁰⁵⁾ as smokers are inclined to underestimate their smoking habits or deny smoking ⁽²⁰³⁾. This social desirability bias is greater in certain groups where smoking is considered less desirable, such as those who are pregnant, on an intervention to stop smoking, with smoking-related health conditions, and from certain religions ^(206; 207); this was evidenced in a systematic review that compared self-reported smoking status to cotinine, a biological measure of exposure to tobacco smoke ⁽²⁰⁴⁾. These biological measures, which are recommended to validate self-reports of smoking status, have shown that interviews are more likely to correctly identify smokers and non-smokers than self-administered questionnaires ⁽²⁰³⁾.

It is important that questionnaires collect information on all forms of smoking (e.g., cigars, pipe tobacco, roll tobacco), not just cigarettes ⁽²⁰⁵⁾. Information should also be collected on frequency of current and former smoking (i.e., number of cigarettes per day), duration of abstinence, and exposure time to tobacco ⁽²⁰⁵⁾. When 10 of the major US surveys that collected data on tobacco use were reviewed, data on cigars, smokeless tobacco and menthol cigarettes were limited ⁽²⁰⁸⁾. Passive smoking/second-hand smoke is also important, however, exposure data is limited ⁽²⁰⁹⁾. Furthermore, development and validation of surveys to measure use of electronic cigarette (e-cigarettes) and non-nicotine delivery systems is lacking ⁽²¹⁰⁾. In addition, surveys use inconsistent terminology, with vaping devices/pens often not being mentioned alongside e-cigarettes, and the inclusion of images is

recommended to depict the wide variety of devices that should be included. Details on device type and nicotine content should also be collected ⁽²¹¹⁾.

It has been observed that tobacco-specific questionnaires often generate lower estimates of tobacco use behaviour than general lifestyle surveys, and the introduction to the questionnaire, question context and ordering are all important considerations, although further research in this area is required ⁽²⁰⁸⁾. One systematic review from 1994 noted that very few studies reported the exact wording of the questions asked, which the authors considered “critical information” as responses are influenced by how the question is phrased and their order of presentation ⁽²⁰³⁾. Finally, there are concerns regarding inadequate translation and validation of smoking questionnaires for ethnic minority groups; once translated the words/concepts may be interpreted differently, and questions may not be culturally appropriate ⁽²⁰⁶⁾.

Anthropometry and basic health indicators

Anthropometric measurements are frequently collected alongside demographic and lifestyle information to provide context to the population under study. There is a great deal of variation in the quality of the information collected using these measures as some studies rely on self-reported height and weight information while others have these measurements collected by trained researchers ^(212; 213; 214). Some studies may provide participants with detailed instructions on how to take the measurements to maximise the quality of the self-reported information collected. Certain populations may be more likely to mis-report height and weight than others; for example, older people may be affected by memory impairments whilst women are more likely to underreport their weight ⁽²¹²⁾. In order to obtain the most accurate anthropometric measurements, weighing scales should be calibrated and stadiometers set up against a wall ⁽²¹⁵⁾. Repeated measurements should be taken. Similarly, basic health information such as blood pressure and simple questions on self-reported health status may be asked. Similar to height and weight measurements, blood pressure should be taken using a calibrated machine and multiple measures should be taken ⁽²¹⁵⁾. Ideally, the participant should be sitting down with their feet elevated prior to taking the measurements.

5.4 Quality considerations in the coding and management of demographic and lifestyle data

Demographics

Like other national organisations, the UK Office for National Statistics (ONS) recognises that variation in definitions and survey questions make it hard to harmonise and compare demographic data ⁽²¹⁶⁾. The UK ONS has classified sets of related categories to harmonise data derived from different sources. Examples include the National Statistics Country Classification which provides each country with a unique code ⁽²¹⁷⁾. Alternatively, countries and their subdivisions can be coded according to the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) coding system, ISO 3166 ⁽²¹⁸⁾. Another classification system is the ONS Standard Occupational Classification 2020, which codes occupations by their skill level and specialisation ⁽²¹⁹⁾, and similar lists exist from the European Commission's multilingual European Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations (ESCO) system ⁽²²⁰⁾. The National Statistics Socio-economic classification (NS-SEC) records employment status and conditions of occupation, for example, whether an individual is an employer, self-employed or an employee, their occupation title, and a description of their job duties ⁽²²¹⁾. This information can be coded, such as 1 for "Employers – large organisations" and 3 for "Senior managers or administrators". The ONS has also created a guide for collecting and classifying ethnic, religion, and national identity data ⁽²²²⁾ and is also working on a guide for gender data collection.

When collecting demographic information, researchers must be aware of the regulations surrounding the use and storage of personal information, defined as information (or a combination of information) that can identify an individual ⁽²²³⁾. Examples include name, date of birth, address, and online identifiers such as IP address. A second category to consider is sensitive or 'special category' data, for example, sexual orientation, race, ethnicity, and health data ⁽²²⁴⁾. Both categories require researchers to comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) for their country. Prior to taking part in research, participants must be informed of how their personal data will be used and give their consent; their personal data cannot be lawfully used for any other purpose. Therefore, at the point of study design, researchers should consider how their data might be used/stored following study completion (e.g., sharing on data repositories for use by third parties) and ensure participants consent to these future uses of their data. Anonymisation (removal of direct and indirect identifiers) allows data to be shared and reused in an ethical way and should also be considered in study design and collection phase (e.g., using "region" rather than "address" when asking for location details) ⁽²²⁵⁾.

Physical activity and sedentary behaviour

Physical activity data can be reported in many ways. It can be expressed as measured activity levels (e.g., minutes of activity per week) or it can be categorised into levels of activity, however, the classifications/categories may differ between studies/methods. For example, the EPIC physical activity index has 4-levels (inactive, moderately inactive, moderately active and active) ⁽²²⁶⁾, whereas others have reported a different set of classifications (e.g., inactive, moderately active and highly active) with different threshold criteria ⁽²²⁷⁾. Alternatively, physical activity can be expressed as a score, such as the Baecke PAQ ⁽²²⁸⁾, which are harder to interpret ⁽¹⁹⁴⁾. These differences in reporting make it difficult to accurately compare some studies.

Prior to using physical activity data, researchers should pre-define their quality control protocol. For accelerometers, this could include thresholds to determine whether the device has been worn for sufficient time and to identify extremely high-count values ^(229; 230). Data is then typically 'cleaned' to remove invalid and incomplete activities to reduce measurement error. However, such criteria are often not published, which reduces consistency between studies. Guidelines are available to assist researchers when preparing data from the International PAQ, such as recommending hours are converted to minutes and providing threshold values to identify outliers ⁽²³¹⁾. Ainsworth et al recommended that guidelines to "reduce data analysis error" are created, such as developing standard methodologies to adjust for reporting errors in PAQ and creating an online resource to assist researchers in their data processing ⁽²³²⁾.

Similar to dietary assessments, self-reported physical activity is often misreported in certain population groups, such as BMI, age and sex ⁽²³³⁾. Non-occupational activity from the EPIC study's past-year recall reported greater agreement with accelerometer data if the participants were male, had a lower BMI and were younger ⁽²³⁴⁾. Other studies have also reported lower agreement in those who are obese or older (≥ 50 years) compared with their normal weight and younger counterparts, respectively ^(235; 236). Choice of method may in part be responsible, for example, tools that do not accurately measure low intensity activities, such as walking, are not recommended for older adults ⁽²³³⁾. Therefore, analysis should adjust for potential mis-reporters. Days of the week recorded are also an important factor to consider. Each day of the week should be sufficiently covered in the sample during data collection and statistical models should be adjusted for days recorded ⁽²⁰¹⁾. As mentioned, measurements also vary *within* devices (e.g., accelerometers may be worn on the wrist, hip or ankle in different studies) so these differences should also be considered when combining data.

Smoking status

Categories to define smoking status vary between questionnaires. There is debate over the term “current use” for tobacco or electronic cigarettes ⁽²¹⁰⁾, for example, if there are only three categories to choose from (never smoked, former smoker and current smoker), then asking about smoking habits during the last month will group recent experimenters and occasional users alongside daily users (who have a much greater exposure) in the “current smoker” category. Even if standard questionnaires are used, the measures reported can also differ. For example, the MONICA study classified “regular cigarette smokers” as daily smokers, which were split into light-moderate smokers (1-19 cigarettes/day) and heavy smokers (≥ 20 /day) ⁽¹⁰⁰⁾, whereas others using the MONICA smoking questionnaire grouped all into “current smokers” only ⁽¹⁰¹⁾. The PATH questionnaire includes a different definition of “current smokers”, defined as those who have “ever smoked cigarettes, even one or two puffs; smoked at least 100 cigarettes in their entire life; and now smoke every day or some days” ⁽⁹⁹⁾. Therefore, surveys lack consensus on smoking status classifications and efforts to standardise and harmonise data across surveys is recommended ⁽⁹⁸⁾.

5.5 Use and analysis of demographic and lifestyle data

As briefly mentioned above, demographic and lifestyle data have many uses within nutrition research. Large nutrition surveys typically use this data to stratify their population group. For example, the UK’s National Diet and Nutrition Survey split their findings according to age and sex, allowing for comparison with age and sex-specific dietary recommendations ⁽²³⁷⁾. Their data is also segmented by region and income to identify trends within the population, such as the percentage of the population on higher versus lower incomes who meet dietary recommendations ⁽²³⁸⁾. Others have used demographic and lifestyle data to investigate relationships with more complex dietary outcomes, e.g., impact of location, education, income, household size, nationality, marital status and/or smoking status on dietary patterns ^(239; 240) and diet quality ⁽²⁴¹⁾. These data can also be used for more complex statistical analyses, such as multivariate models to identify which demographic and lifestyle factors are predictors of dietary intake ^(242; 243). The inclusion of demographic and lifestyle data within the statistical analysis of dietary intake and consumer behaviour data provide additional context to help government policy makers identify and develop appropriate public health strategies for targeted groups of the population, such as the need to promote fruit and vegetable intakes in lower socioeconomic groups; the lowest intakes are typically found in those with the lowest incomes in the UK ⁽²³⁸⁾. These findings also have the potential to assist with product development within industry.

D4.6 Report on data quality and usability assessment strategies

It is important for researchers to understand who is participating in the research. Therefore, it is good practice to collect demographic and lifestyle data to enable the participant characteristics to be sufficiently described within publications ^(244; 245). Firstly, this data identifies who the findings are generalisable to ⁽²⁴⁶⁾. For example, lower socioeconomic or ethnic minority groups may be under-represented in the sample, limiting the validity and applicability of research findings to these groups; it was reported that less than 10% of randomised controlled trials published in four leading journals included key data to identify the sample's socioeconomic status, with the authors calling for “more transparency” in publications ⁽²⁴⁴⁾. Secondly, demographic and lifestyle data may identify important differences between intervention and control groups in randomised controlled trials, which may be considered to confound the findings of the study, such as significant differences in age, ethnicity, physical activity levels, etc. between groups. These data should be collected for inclusion in statistical models to control for these potentially confounding factors, which strengthen the findings compared with uncontrolled statistical analysis.

Table 5.1 Considerations when collecting and evaluating demographic and lifestyle data

<u>Data</u>	<u>Methodology</u>	<u>Advantages</u>	<u>Disadvantages</u>	<u>Appropriate Use</u>
Demographic	Surveys/questionnaires	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Postal: Accessible to all populations such as those who do not have internet access · Electronic: Cost and time effective · Can be administered to a large sample at once · Broad range of data can be collected at once 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Postal: Expensive (e.g., printing, and postal costs) · Postal: Time-consuming to send, receive and process data · Electronic: Limited use among those without internet access/limited ability to use technology · Limited response rates · Responses may be subject to social desirability bias · Lack of standardisation · Frequent use 'prefer not to say' responses 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Research · Commercial
General lifestyle	Surveys/questionnaires (e.g., GLQ)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Can be administered to a large sample at once · Can focus on a single aspect of lifestyle or measure overall lifestyle · Can be tailored to health conditions/disease risk 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · One questionnaire will not fit all populations · Responses may be subject to social desirability bias · Lack of standardisation · Often lengthy · Require regularly updating to reflect current lifestyle habits 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Research · Clinical

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Physical activity	Surveys/questionnaires	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More cost and time effective • Can be administered to a large sample at once 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited response rates • Responses may be subject to social desirability bias • Lack of standardisation • Relies on recall (may not be suitable for children and older adults) • Light activities under-represented (need adjusting for older adults) • Many questionnaires to choose from so extensive research is required to select the most appropriate one 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research • Clinical
	Web/smartphone applications (examples: BeWell24, ACT24)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More cost and time effective • Can be administered to a large sample at once 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responses may be subject to social desirability bias • Not accessible to those without internet access/limited ability to use technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research
	Activity monitors (examples: accelerometers, pedometers, heart rate monitors, multi-sensors)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction in reporting bias • Less burden on participant 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expensive to distribute to a large sample • Subject to reactivity bias • Accuracy between devices differs • Not all activities can be detected by a device • Commercial devices not designed for research (e.g. FitBit, Garmin) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research • Commercial • Consumer
Sedentary behaviour	Surveys/questionnaires	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More cost and time effective • Can be administered to a large sample at once 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responses may be subject to social desirability bias • Lack of standardisation • Relies on recall (may not be suitable for children and older adults) • Many questionnaires to choose from 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research • Clinical

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	Monitors (examples: inclinometer devices, BeWell24, ACT24)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduction in reporting bias Less burden on participant 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Devices can be expensive to distribute to a large sample 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research Clinical
Smoking status	Surveys/questionnaires	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interviews more likely to generate accurate responses than questionnaires 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Few questionnaires specifically designed to assess smoking status Subject to social desirability bias (esp. among certain groups) Exposure to passive smoking often not considered 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research Clinical

Table 5.2: Quality Considerations for Collection / Handling / Analysis of Demographic and Lifestyle Data

Data Collection	Data Management	Data Analysis
Use of a validated tool/limited modification of existing tool	Coding systems to harmonise data e.g., UK Office of National Statistics classification systems	Consideration of under/over reporting e.g., weight, physical activity, smoking levels
Tool is appropriate for the target population e.g., electronic vs paper-based	Handling of personal information and sensitive/special category data in compliance with GDPR	Accurate representation of target population (i.e., were there similarities among non-respondents)
Suitable wording and response options of questions to discourage the use of a 'prefer not to say' response	Data between studies should be classified in a similar way such as the classification of physically inactive should be consistent or the definition of 'current smoker' for example	Significant demographic differences between control and intervention groups that may confound study results
Validation of self-reported data via healthcare professional/researcher	Data adjusted for misreporting where an inappropriate tool has been used or data not collected over a suitable range of days	
Appropriate data collection period for the tool being used (e.g., multiple days of collection)		

Table 5.3a: Analytical potential of physical activity and sedentary behaviour data

Methodology	Data collected	Step count	Activity duration (e.g. min/day)	Activity intensity	MET scores (e.g. MET min/week)	Other measures of activity (e.g. EE, PAL, MVPA)	Activity category (e.g. low, moderate, high)	Sedentary behaviour (e.g. total sitting time)
General lifestyle questionnaire	Paper-based or electronic questionnaires	X	✓	X	X	X	✓*	X
Physical activity questionnaire	Paper-based or electronic questionnaires, e.g., International Physical Activity Questionnaire	X	✓	✓*	✓*		✓*	✓*
Activity log/diary	Record of daily activities	X	✓	✓				✓*
Sedentary behaviour questionnaire	Paper-based or electronic questionnaires	✓	X	X				✓
Pedometer	Wearable device	✓	X	X				X
Accelerometer	Wearable device, e.g. ActiGraph, ActivPAL	✓	✓	✓**	✓	✓	✓	✓*
GPS	Wearable device	X	X	✓	X	✓***	X	X
Heart rate monitors	Wearable device	X	X	✓***	X	✓***	X	X
Multi-sensor devices	Wearable device, e.g. SenseWear	X	✓	✓	X	✓	✓*	✓*

Commercial activity trackers	Wearable device, e.g. FitBit, Garmin, Apple	✓				✓		
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* Dependent on the level of detail collected in the specific questionnaires or features included in the specific tools. Further information can be found in ^(153; 155; 160) [

** Limited for certain weight-bearing activities, swimming and cycling.

*** Lower validity and reliability than other measures (e.g. heart rate is influenced by other factors; GPS is limited for monitoring higher speeds).

GPS: Global Positioning System; METs: metabolic equivalents; MVPA: moderate to vigorous physical activity; PAL: physical activity level; EE: energy expenditure

Table 5.3b: Analytical potential of smoking data

Methodology	Data collected	Current smoking status	Duration of smoking (e.g. age started, duration)	History of smoking habits (if no longer a current smoker)	Frequency of smoking (e.g. cigarettes/day)	Type of smoking product (e.g. cigarettes, cigar, pipe)	Exposure to passive smoking	Use of non-nicotine smoking products
Smoking questionnaire	Paper-based or electronic questionnaires	✓	✓*	✓*	✓*	✓*	✓*	✓*
General lifestyle questionnaire	Paper-based or electronic questionnaires	✓	✓*	✓*	✓*	✓*	X	X

Based on typical questionnaires for each methodology. * Dependent on the level of detail collected in the specific questionnaires

6 Development and use of quality framework

Quality assessment frameworks

Quality assessment frameworks are not designed to recommend a single ‘best’ approach. Instead, they provide a consistent systematic approach to assessing whether a certain aspect/thing is fit for the intended purpose and provide suggestions on how to approach different situations ⁽²⁴⁷⁾. Examples of quality assessment frameworks previously developed include the framework for assessing studies for inclusion in systematic reviews ⁽²⁴⁷⁾ and assessing quality of clinical research datasets ⁽²⁴⁸⁾.

Whilst there are numerous quality assessment initiatives/tools which have been developed for the FNS area ⁽²⁴⁹⁾ such as Nutritools ^(16; 250), Quisper (<https://quisper.eu/>), and DAPA (<https://dapa-toolkit.mrc.ac.uk/>) there are no such tools available to assess the quality of previously collected data for reuse. With the development and launch of FNS Cloud there is a need for a framework to assess the appropriateness of data (quality) for reuse to answer specific research questions so that high quality research is conducted.

Rationale for this work

The rationale for undertaking this work is that it will support data reuse in the area of FNS. This is a key aim of FNS-Cloud. Large amounts of often publicly funded, money are used to generate large datasets yet frequently, once the primary research objectives have been achieved these datasets do not get exploited for further use. Therefore, it is recommended that instead of collecting new data, datasets already in existence could be reused or used in combination with other datasets to answer new research questions. In order for efficient data merging to take place and for high quality research to be conducted there is a need for a structured quality assessment framework in the area of FNS to ensure that datasets are selected for reuse following a standardised process to assess whether they are *fit for the intended research purpose*. Thus, the aim of this work is to develop a quality assessment framework for use in FNS Cloud to support researchers in their decision-making process of whether previously collected datasets under consideration are *fit for their intended research purposes*.

Description of methodology undertaken

This framework follows the process for developing quality assessment tools, as described by Whiting et al., (2017) ⁽²⁴⁷⁾. Whiting et al.’s approach consists of three stages, initial steps, tool development and dissemination as described within Figure 6.1.

Figure 6.1: Steps to develop a quality assessment tool ⁽²⁴⁷⁾

An overview of the actions taken, within this body of work, to follow the steps outlined is summarised in Table 6.4. As per the guidelines laid out by Whiting et al., robust tools are developed based on evidence and then refined by expert consensus. Thus, the development of a quality framework for use in FNS Cloud consisted of two phases: 1) review of the literature on indicators of quality across each of the data domains, 2) development of a quality assessment tool and review by experts in the field. A domain-based approach to the literature review was taken, focusing on specific indicators of quality under 4 headings, namely, methods and collection, underlying data sources, data management, uses and analysis. Following this, indicators of quality specific to each data domain were identified and collected from the review. It was decided to develop a flow chart for each data domain for this quality assessment framework. Flow charts and ‘decision trees’ (another form of decision making support process) have previously been used to inform healthcare decision making ^(251; 252; 253) such as for the translation of clinical cancer guideline recommendations ⁽²⁵³⁾. The flow charts developed in this instance consist of a series of questions under each heading from the review. These questions can be answered with yes, no, don’t know or specific responses. Each response may be followed by one or more follow-up questions, ultimately finishing in a personalised message based on the user’s responses. These messages are not designed to definitively tell a data user whether they should use the datasets being considered, but rather to help them consider additional quality and ‘fitness for use’ factors they may not have previously considered, thereby supporting them in the decision-making

process. For this reason, it was decided not to provide a numerical scoring system or rating to this tool, rather that the data user should be provided with sufficient information through the personalised messages delivered to use their own expert judgement in the final decision of whether the data under consideration is suitable for use within their specified research question.

Use of scores to evaluate quality have been shown to be inaccurate in the assessment of quality of studies for use in systematic reviews ⁽²⁵⁴⁾ and meta-analyses ⁽²⁵⁵⁾. A similar non-score based approach was taken in the development of the GRACE principles which evaluate the quality of observational studies of comparative effectiveness whereby the authors state that even imperfect studies can provide useful information if they are well designed, conducted, analysed and consciously reported ⁽²⁵⁶⁾. Furthermore, during a virtual workshop held amongst members of the FNS-Cloud consortium in April of 2020, there was a general consensus amongst attendees that decision on whether to map/merge different datasets should be specific to the individual research question. Due to the broad and varied nature of research questions (which may be answered using dietary intake, consumer behaviour, demographic and lifestyle data) it would be inappropriate to provide definitive answers on whether data are appropriate for use without prior knowledge of the specific research question and individual datasets being considered. Personalised messages will be developed to be delivered to potential data users to help them better understand the data they are considering and notify them of factors they should be aware of prior to using the data for their analysis.

Results of flow chart development

Individual flow charts were developed for demographic, dietary intake, consumer behaviour and lifestyle data. Within these there were 4 main branches in each: methods and collection, underlying data sources, dataset management, uses and analysis. Examples of the branches developed for dietary intake data are shown in Figures 6. 2 – 6.4. The blue colour indicates that if a researcher reaches a blue box they will be shown a message for consideration specific to their own dataset. Following completion of all of the flow chart branches, a summary report containing all of the considerations messages specific to the researchers' data will be produced (Figure 6.5).

Figure 6.2 Quality assessment of the methods of collection of dietary intake data

Figure 6.3 Quality assessment of underlying data sources used in dietary intake data

Figure 6.4. Quality assessment of dataset management in dietary intake data

D4.6 Report on data quality and usability assessment strategies

You have completed the quality assessment for the XX dataset. A summary of the considerations specific to your data under each of the headings are displayed below.

Methods: The subjective 24-hour recall method has been used to collect this data. This 24-hour recall was conducted using a novel tool or combination of a novel tool and researcher.	
Validated- Comparison to another method	The tool used to collect this data has been reported to be validated by comparing it to another method of dietary intake data collection. It would be important for you to fully understand how valid the tool was that was considered and which method it was compared against.
Validated population and sample size	When using a validated tool it is important that the population in which the tool was validated is reported to be similar to the population considered in the dataset. It is always important that tools are used in the population in which they are validated. For example, if the tool has been validated for use in children it may not be appropriate for use in adult populations. Caution should be taken if the number of people included in the validation study(s) is very small.
Underlying data sources	
Food composition database. Source unknown	The source of the food composition database used by this dataset is either unknown or not named. When using dietary intake data it is important to understand where the underlying food composition data comes from. Food composition databases have been shown to be one of the most influential determinants in comparing energy and nutrient intakes among different commercial apps. This is particularly important if a researcher is considering using data arising from a technology-based method, as these are often 'user determined' or a combination of user derived data and published datasets, thus making it difficult to determine the quality of the nutrient intake data produced.
Portion size. Quantified using estimations	It is important for accuracy and to reduce the prevalence of dietary under-/over-reporters that portion size is quantified. In this dataset, portion size was estimated. This may have been done using photos / household measures / average weights from existing data. Portion size estimation may increase the prevalence of dietary under reporters. Online tools incorporating images of multiple portion sizes may reduce this error, however these methods rely on participant memory so may not be appropriate for all population groups.
Nutrient information. All macro and micronutrients	This dataset contains a wide range of nutrient information on macro and micronutrients. This gives the researcher the option of completing nutrient intake analysis for specific nutrient intakes.
Multiple days collected	Collection of data across multiple days may increase the overall data quality, as nutrient intakes can be calculated as a daily average, giving a more accurate representation of an individual' diet. Collection of data across both week and weekend days is important as an individual's diet often varies between weekdays and weekend days.
Data handling / dataset management	
Identification of misreporters	Identification of under and over-reporters is important to ensure the quality of dietary intake data. Sensitivity analysis may also be completed, repeating the analysis both with and without dietary under/over-reporters to examine the effect they have on the analysis.
Use of standardized food coding system	This dataset uses a standardised food classification systems to code its food items. Standardised food coding systems use detailed descriptions of the food items within a dietary intake dataset and are important for accurate identification, and correct allocation of appropriate composition

Figure 6.5. Example output report following completion of quality assessment

Use within and beyond FNS Cloud

As part of the next phase of implementing the quality assessment into FNS-Cloud, the flow charts will undergo a two-step evaluation process: 1) internally by partners of FNS-Cloud with domain specific knowledge; 2) externally by specific members of the EEAB. Following both iterations of the quality assessment framework these will be tested within WP5 under demonstrator 2. The quality assessment framework will be applied to different datasets in order to select appropriate datasets for use in answering two separate research questions.

It is hoped that once these research questions have been answered, the framework will be deployed within FNS-Cloud and used by all data users as one of the first steps in identifying datasets suitable for use in their specific analyses.

Table 6.1: Overview of the process of developing the quality assessment framework

Stage	Quality assessment framework for dietary intake, consumer behaviour, lifestyle and demographic data for FNS Cloud
Stage 1: Initial steps	
1.1 Identify need	A framework for assessing whether the existing dietary intake, consumer behaviour, lifestyle and demographic data is fit for the intended research purpose
1.2 Obtain funding	Part of Food Nutrition Security Cloud (FNS-Cloud) which received funding under the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme (Grant Agreement No. 863059)
1.3 Assemble team	FNS-Cloud Consortium ($n = 35$ partner institutions, $n = \text{X}$ members))
1.4 Manage project	Data quality working group ($n = 13$)
1.5 Define scope	Quality of existing datasets
Stage 2: Tool development	
2.1. Generate items	Starting point: review of literature of quality within each data domain Identification of markers of quality identified from the literature Formation of flow charts for assessing quality
2.2. Agree items	Virtual face-to-face meeting
2.3. Produce first draft	Data quality working group
2.4. Pilot and refine*	Internal feedback from consortium members External feedback from members of the EEAB Use within WP5 demonstrators
Stage 3: Dissemination*	
3.1 Publication	Planned publication and publicly available deliverable
3.2 Website	www.fns-cloud.eu/
3.3 Uptake	Not yet released
3.4 Translations	None planned thus far

EEAB, external expert advisory board

*Stage 2.4 ad stage 3 will be updated once the assessment framework has been finalised

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